

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

November, 05-06 2022
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

Challenges in planning adjuvant radiotherapy incervical cancer patients with bilateral J-J stents

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Introduction: Cervical cancer multimodal treatment causes 75% urethral complications, during surgery or radiotherapy that induces free radicals and vascular damage. J-J stent placement, due to renal function preservation, increase infection, encrustation and obstruction risk.

Materials and Methods: A 38 year old patient with FIGO Ib3 cervical cancer, was treated with radical hysterectomy. Bilateral J-J stents were placed due to renal calculus immediately after. Treatment continued with adjuvant radiotherapy. Following 10th fraction, patient presented with fatigue, fewer, diarrhea, and sepsis signs and symptoms, in absence of apparent infection (negative urine/blood cultures, stent swabs, stool samples, additional imaging procedures) and J-J stents were removed, accompanied by three weeks antibiotic course (quinolones, carbapenems and colistin), with general condition improved and postoperative radiotherapy continued. Upon finalizing the radiotherapy cycle, pelvic MR were conducted – without infection signs. Three weeks later, due to anuria and hydronephrosis grade 2, control multislice CT showed distal ureter and bladder fundus fibrosis.

Results: VMAT radiotherapy with 4000cGy/20fr followed by three cycle brachytherapy (600cGy per application) was conducted, respecting recommendations for organs at risk. J-J stent mean dose was 4171cGy on the left side, 2274cGy on the right side, respectively.

Determining whether changing in stent structure was caused, under the same conditions J-J stent were irradiated, using 9000cGy/6fr. Stent density prior to radiation was 1884 HU, and after 2225 HU (patient stent density measured 2700 HU prior to radiotherapy).

Conclusion: All above mentioned factors can be contributing in urethral microenvironment, or J-J stent density alteration after implantation and radiotherapy can potentially cause of that change in symbiosis with microbiota.

Keywords: cervical cancer, J-J stents, ureteral strictures, antibiotics, postoperative radiotherapy

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2022**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

CIP – Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteka Mатице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (2022 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress,
November, 05-06 2022 Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula,
Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. - Novi Sad : Institut za
Onkologiju Vojvodine, 2022 (Novi Sad : NS digiprint).
– 56 str. : ilustr. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200.

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 78911241